

An automate failure recovery for synchronous distributed database system

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ABSTRACT

Periodically, researchers have been sharing their constant attempts to improve the existing methods for data replication in distributed database system. The main goal is to work for an efficient distributed environment. An efficient environment may handle huge amount of data and preserve data availability. The occasionally failures in distributed systems will affect the end results, such as data loss, income loss etc. Thus, to prevent the data loss and guarantee the continuity of the business, many organizations have applied disaster recovery solutions in their system. One of the widely used is database replication, because it guarantees data safety and availability. However, disaster still can occur in database replication. Hence, an automatic failure recovery technique called distributed database replication with fault tolerance (DDR-FT) has been proposed in this research. DDR-FT uses heartbeat message for node monitoring. Subsequently, a foundation of binary vote assignment for fragmented database (BVAFD) replication technique has been used. In DDR-FT, the data nodes are continuously monitored while auto reconfiguring for automatic failure recovery. From the conducted experiments, it is proved that DDR-FT can preserve system availability. It shows that DDR-FT technique provides a convenient approach to system availability for distributed database replication in real time environment.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, getting access to high quality data can help to enhance the quality of life both for those working in the organization and for the people. Hence, it is crucial to ensure the database system is well managed and secure. There are two types of database systems which are centralized database system and distributed database system. Centralized database system is a database that is located, stored and maintained in a single location. When the single database server is crashed or mishap happens, everything will be lost. Thus, to increase and preserve the data availability and reliability, it is better to store the data in multiple servers rather than in one server [1]–[3]. This method is called distributed database system [1], [4], [5]. Hence, in the event of disaster, data availability is ensured because distributed systems have higher reliability and incremental growth [6].

Distributed databases systems (DDBS) are a set of logically networked computer databases, managed by different sites, locations and accessible to the user locally or via the Internet for different tasks as a single database by running transactions in parallel [4], [7]. The design of DDBS is a very demanding task since an optimum level of performance must be continuously satisfied [8], [9]. Data availability plays a major role in the success of information systems because data must be always available in order to meet the users' requirements.

Data replication is one of the widely used solutions to ensure data safety and availability in distributed database system [10], [11]. It plays a critical role in promoting business for any organisations, refining the quality of the data, improving data sharing as well as the process for big data analysis [12]. Therefore, the implementation of the data replication method itself can be vital when it involves failure interruption. Particularly, failures occur regularly on the internet, clouds and in scale-out data center networks [13]–[16]. Hence, a fault tolerance method is needed in data replication transaction [17]–[19]. A system using such services are required to be equipped with resources so that the system can guarantee to operate even in the presence of faults [17], [20]–[22]. Fault is supposed to be detected by using a reliable fault detector followed by a recovery technique.

In this research, a data replication technique called binary vote assignment for fragmented database (BVAFD) is combined with a proposed fault tolerance technique called distributed database system with fault tolerance (DDR-FT) with the aimed of assessing the efficiency of synthesizing data replication technique with fault tolerance technique for a better performance of a single database replication transaction in the event of failure. The paper is arranged as follows. Section 2 is the literature review which detailed out about BVAFD data replication technique. In section 3, the methodology describes the procedure of DDR-FT algorithm which is employed within BVAFD framework. The result and discussion is presented in section 4 where the outcomes obtained from a series of experiments that has been tested are discussed in this section. Finally, the conclusion of this research is provided in section 5, conclusion.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Figure 1 shows the concept of binary vote assignment for fragmented database (BVAFD) is copying some data from the primary node to some of the adjacent's nodes [23]. Full replication mechanism may waste a lot of of storage space and consume a lot of bandwidth [24] because it copies all data to all replication nodes. By using BVAFD, the replication execution time is reduced since it only copies some data to some nodes [24], [25]. BVAFD is pacing a new path in distributed database replication as it helps to maximize the write availability with low communication cost [26].

In BVAFD, each node has a primary database table, PDT. PDT will be copied to the neighbours' nodes, NS from the primary node, PS [23]. PS of any PDT and NS are assigned with vote one (1) or vote zero (0). This assignment is treated as an allocation of replicated copies and a vote assigned to the site results in a copy allocated at the neighbour [27] PS of any PDT and NS are assigned with different status depends on their condition. Status = 0 is shown when PS is accessible. Meanwhile, status = 1 is shown when PS is inaccessible or busy.

Figure 1. Examples of data replication in BVAFD

3. RESEARCH METHODS

In this section, distributed database system with fault tolerance (DDR-FT) is proposed by considering fault detection and fault recovery in BVAFD. The monitor node will always monitor all the heartbeat message from all the data nodes. Recovery process will only begin automatically once a fault has been detected. The following notations are defined:

- N_d is a node with data
- N_m is a monitor node
- N'_d is neighbour node, where $d = 1, 2, 3, 4$, or 5
- N_{df} is failure node transformed from N_d .
- F_{∇} is when no failure occurs
- F_{Δ} is when failure occurs
- IP_p is a primary IP address
- IP_v is a virtual IP address

All N_d where $d = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ continuously send a heartbeat message, to N_m . Hence, N_m always monitor all heartbeat messages received from N_d . If N_m does not receives any heartbeat messages from N_d , it will assume $N_d = F_{\Delta}$ and transform N_d to N_{df} . Next, N_m will search the available N'_d of N_{df} . Once N_m get the N'_d , it will assign the N'_d as the backup node for the N_{df} . Then, N'_d will create IP_v contains an IP of N_{df} . Now N'_d will have two IP addresses which are its own IP_p and IP_v of N_{df} . Once N_m detect h=1 from N_{df} , then $N_{df} = F_{\nabla} \rightarrow N_d$, it will delete the IP_v from N_{df} and continue monitoring the nodes.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

In this section, experiments of cases that occur during real time transactions are presented. It involved three replication nodes called node 1, node 2 and node 4 in one distributed database systems. All data in these three servers are supposed to be the same replicated data. Therefore, all the data will be updated synchronously.

4.1. Experiment 1: no failure occurs in any nodes

Figure 2 shows $N_1 = F_{\nabla}$. N_m receives all the heartbeat messages sent from N_d where $d = 1, 2$ and 4 . Thus, it will assume no failure occurred. Figure 3 shows monitor node, N_m receive heartbeat from node 1, 2 and 4. During this time, all N_d are sending their heartbeat message to the N_m without any failure.

Figure 2. Data nodes without any failure occurrence

Figure 3. Monitor node receive heartbeat

4.2. Data node 1 held failure occurrence without DDR-FT

Figure 4 shows $N_1 = F_{\Delta} \rightarrow N_{1f}$ which means a failure occurs during the transaction. Node 1 is not connected through the network. When this happens, N_{1f} will try to reconnect to the N_m every 5 seconds. However, since there is no fault tolerance in this system, this problem will not be solved until it is fixed manually. Any transaction will not be able to proceed until the problem is solved.

```

Select Administrator: Command Prompt - py client.py
[2020-12-14 14:58:36,705] [ping] [INFO] - Sent alive ping as node 1
[2020-12-14 14:58:38,723] [ping] [INFO] - Sent alive ping as node 1
[2020-12-14 14:58:40,738] [ping] [INFO] - Sent alive ping as node 1
[2020-12-14 14:58:42,754] [ping] [INFO] - Sent alive ping as node 1
[2020-12-14 14:58:44,769] [ping] [INFO] - Sent alive ping as node 1
[2020-12-14 14:58:46,769] [ping] [INFO] - Sent alive ping as node 1
[2020-12-14 14:58:48,783] [ping] [INFO] - Sent alive ping as node 1
[2020-12-14 14:58:50,785] [ping] [INFO] - Sent alive ping as node 1
[2020-12-14 14:58:52,798] [ping] [INFO] - Sent alive ping as node 1
[2020-12-14 14:58:54,814] [ping] [INFO] - Sent alive ping as node 1
[2020-12-14 14:58:56,845] [ping] [INFO] - Sent alive ping as node 1
[2020-12-14 14:58:58,847] [ping] [INFO] - Sent alive ping as node 1
[2020-12-14 14:59:00,877] [ping] [INFO] - Sent alive ping as node 1
[2020-12-14 14:59:02,986] [ping] [INFO] - Sent alive ping as node 1
[2020-12-14 14:59:05,002] [ping] [INFO] - Sent alive ping as node 1
[2020-12-14 14:59:06,798] [operations] [WARNING] - I'm disconnected!
[2020-12-14 14:59:08,986] [operations] [DEBUG] - Connection refused by the server
Trying to reconnect in 5 seconds
[2020-12-14 14:59:14,095] [operations] [DEBUG] - Attempting Connection
[2020-12-14 14:59:16,127] [operations] [DEBUG] - Connection refused by the server
Trying to reconnect in 5 seconds
[2020-12-14 14:59:21,143] [operations] [DEBUG] - Attempting Connection
[2020-12-14 14:59:23,174] [operations] [DEBUG] - Connection refused by the server
Trying to reconnect in 5 seconds
[2020-12-14 14:59:28,190] [operations] [DEBUG] - Attempting Connection
[2020-12-14 14:59:30,205] [operations] [DEBUG] - Connection refused by the server
Trying to reconnect in 5 seconds
    
```

Figure 4. Node 1 attempting to send it heartbeat

4.3. Data node 1 held failure occurrence with DDR-FT

Figure 5 shows $N_1 = F_{\Delta} \rightarrow N_{1f}$ which means a failure occurs during the transaction. In this experiment, DDR-FT has been applied in the BVAFD for failure detection and recovery purposes. Node 1 is not connected through the network which will be detected by monitoring node. The monitor node then will begin the recovery process. In this experiment, N_1 do not send any heartbeat messages to the N_m . As shown in Figure 6, N_m does not receive any heartbeat messages from N_1 . Hence, it will assume $N_1 = F_{\Delta}$ and transform N_1 to N_{1f} . N_m will begin the recovery process. N_m will search for any N'_d where $d = 2$ or 4 to backup N_1 .

Figure 5. Failure nodes without fault tolerance

```

operations.log                                ping.log
1 [2020-12-14 14:43:32,412] [operations] [INFO] - Node 1 has joined with
  session ID: bd21af13363d4bacb4f33cfcfb480732d
2 [2020-12-14 14:46:38,238] [operations] [INFO] - Node 1 has joined with
  session ID: 8f383be386f641fdbae023fd67efac4
3 [2020-12-14 14:49:03,375] [operations] [INFO] - Node 2 has joined with
  session ID: adcb2705c9c34a6587253342d604fb1d
4 [2020-12-14 14:54:36,834] [operations] [INFO] - Node 4 has joined with
  session ID: f31757c991ae45618201d4401d54ea89
5 [2020-12-14 15:00:02,757] [operations] [CRITICAL] - Node 1 disconnected.
  Looking up neighbors for recovery
6 [2020-12-14 15:00:02,759] [operations] [INFO] - Found neighbors : ['2'].
  Assigning 2 for recovery
7 [2020-12-14 15:00:04,353] [operations] [INFO] - Recovery Success by node 2
  with new Virtual IP as: 192.168.0.102. Updating records...
    
```

Figure 6. Failure recovery process from monitor node operations log

After N_m found the available neighbor node, for example in this experiment, N'_2 , N'_2 then will create an IPv of N_{1f} which is IP address for N1 as shown in Figure 7. Figure 8 shows N'_2 now have two IP addresses, which are $IP_p = 192.168.0.101$ and the $IP_v = 192.168.0.102$. From figure 8, N'_2 have two IP addresses which are its own IP address and virtual IP address from the failure node, N_{1f} .

```
06:17,456] [operations] [INFO] - Received recovery request. Recovering node 1
06:17,456] [operations] [INFO] - creating virtual IP address: 192.168.0.102
06:17,456] [operations] [CRITICAL] - netsh interface ipv4 add address "Ethernet0" 192.168.0.102 255.255.255.0
06:17,782] [operations] [CRITICAL] - Success
06:17,797] [operations] [INFO] - Successfully created secondary IP as 192.168.0.102 Notifying Server...
```

Figure 7. Node 2 receive recovery request

Figure 8. IP address for node 2

5. CONCLUSION

This study proposed an automatic failure recovery technique called DDR-FT. DDR-FT focuses on the detection of fault and failure recovery. It is run in a replication technique called BVAFD. From the series of experiments that have been conducted, it is proved that DDR-FT can preserve system availability in BVAFD during the event of a failure. It also shows that DDR-FT provides a convenient approach to data availability for distributed database replication in real time environment. However, DDR-FT can be improved in many ways. As we know, data consistency is very important in distributed database. Currently DDR-FT does not support post recovery process. In future, DDR-FT will handle the data consistency after the failure node is operating again. In addition, this method is aimed to be fully implemented in various systems and compare the performances against other existing fault tolerance methods. The framework will be expanded to cover not only the ability to detect and recover failure, but also allow the application to automatically access various recovery and masking mechanisms.

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